

Cosmic Expansion Drives Galactic Dynamics

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(Dated: February 3, 2026)

The cosmic acceleration scale cH and the extra-Newtonian acceleration inferred from galaxy rotation and velocity dispersion are on the same order of magnitude, $\sim 10^{-10} \text{ ms}^{-2}$, but opposite in direction—thus often disregarded as a numerical coincidence. However, the correspondence becomes natural when the vacuum is viewed not as an empty void but a physical, relativistic continuum in flux. Much like in hydrodynamics, an outflow of spatial substance from a local system into expanding, sparser surroundings pulls bodies together, whereas inflow from denser sources pushes them apart. The universal field arising from the immense efflux of space expanding isotropically cannot be canceled by the shell theorem—which strictly holds for stationary rather than dispersing matter—nor curtailed by distance, as the quadratic rise in galaxy count outweighs the inverse falloff of individual potentials. By partitioning the universal flux into local and cosmic components, we derive the generalized baryonic Faber–Jackson and Tully–Fisher relations, matching observations without dark matter or modified gravity. Accordingly, structures emerge on ever larger scales as the turnaround radii of efflux–influx balance lengthen with the thinning cosmic density from the early universe to the present sparseness, manifested in the cosmic gravitational redshift.

I. INTRODUCTION

The extra-Newtonian acceleration of $\sim 10^{-10} \text{ ms}^{-2}$ ascribed to dark matter or modified gravity is remarkably congruent with the cosmic acceleration scale cH [1–10]. While this correspondence is often set aside as a numerical coincidence—on the grounds that no net local gravitational force arises from the large-scale, isotropic distribution of matter—it is worth noting that the classical shell theorem strictly holds for stationary matter. However, for dispersing matter, Birkhoff’s theorem leads to a different conclusion: the expansion itself generates a gravitational field

$$\mathbf{a}_R = -\nabla\phi_R, \quad (1)$$

extending from the dense primordial era across the causal radius $R = ct$ to the sparse present, where $t = 1/H \approx 13.8$ Gyr is the Hubble time. The universal potential $\phi_R = -GM_R/R$ of the total baryonic mass M_R also manifests itself as a Machian origin of inertia [11]. The overall potential increases with distance, since the quadratic increase in the number of galaxies outweighs the inverse falloff.

Yet, a fundamental tension remains: how could the outward acceleration driving cosmic expansion give rise to the inward acceleration governing galactic dynamics? This apparent paradox is resolved if one views the vacuum not as an empty void but as a physical continuum in flux. Much like in hydrodynamics, an outflow of ‘spatial substance’ from a local system into its expanding, sparser surroundings effectively pulls bodies together, whereas inflow from denser sources pushes them apart.

Contrary to common belief, a physical spatial continuum endowed with energy density need not conflict with established experimental evidence. While the Michelson–Morley experiment ruled out a mechanical medium carrying photons—the luminiferous ether—it did not exclude a relativistic continuum composing photons themselves. In such a physical plenum, *phase* velocities along both interferometer arms are invariably equal, regardless of motion.

In this picture, photon rays paired with opposite phases form an undulating transparent substance [12–14]. Its density-dependent *wave speed* c [15–17] characterizes the propagation of both gravitational and electromagnetic waves—understood respectively as longitudinal perturbations in photon density and transverse torsions in photon phase—paralleling early efforts for unification through spatial substance [18–22]. Accordingly, rather than a formal metric expansion of spacetime, space emerging from matter through annihilation reactions would merely extend the otherwise source-free geometrization of gravitation in general relativity.

We proceed to show that the flux of space, driven by density gradients within the spatial substance itself, provides a consistent account of galactic dynamics and cosmic expansion without postulating dark matter, dark energy, or modifications to gravity.

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II. SPACE IN FLUX

As a physical substance, space satisfies the continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = \Gamma. \quad (2)$$

Here, the spatial energy density ρ evolves and flows with velocity \mathbf{v} along gradients as space emerges from matter at a rate Γ through elementary particle reactions, notably annihilation [14, 23, 24]. Governed by the conservation of the quantum of action, these transformations from discrete particles to the spatial continuum can be examined using an open-access package [25].

The continuity equation in integral form—the Reynolds transport theorem generalized with a source term—relates the rate of space generation to the changing energy density within a volume V and its expansion through the surface \mathbf{S} :

$$\int_V \Gamma dV = \frac{d}{dt} \int_V \rho dV + \oint_{\partial V} \rho \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{S}. \quad (3)$$

For a universe expanding isotropically with radial velocity $\mathbf{v} = c\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, multiplying Eq. (3) by $4\pi G/c^2$ reveals the corresponding change in gravitational flux:

$$\begin{aligned} -4\pi G \int_{V_R} \Gamma_M dV &= \frac{4\pi G}{c^2} \int_{V_R} \frac{d\rho}{dt} dV + 4\pi G \oint_{\partial V_R} \rho_M c \hat{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_R \\ \Leftrightarrow -4\pi \frac{\partial}{\partial t} GM_R &= \frac{4\pi G}{c^2} \int_{V_R} \frac{d\rho}{dt} dV + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \oint_{\partial V_R} \mathbf{a}_R \cdot d\mathbf{S}_R. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, the mass density $\rho_M = \rho/c^2$, of Poisson's equation, $\nabla^2 \phi_R = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a}_R = 4\pi G \rho_M$, evolves at the rate $\partial_t \rho_M = \Gamma_M = \Gamma/c^2$. For a non-translating or non-spinning universe, the time derivative acts solely on ρ .

The last term in Eq. (4), the universal flux, $\Phi_R = \oint \mathbf{a}_R \cdot d\mathbf{S}_R = -4\pi GM_R$ by Gauss's theorem, diminishes as matter transforms into space through high-energy processes in stars, supernovae, and active galactic nuclei. Given the gravitational mass–energy equivalence $\phi_R = -GM_R/R = -c^2$, the rate of volumetric change $\partial_t \Phi_R = -4\pi c^2 \partial_t R = -4\pi c^3$ derives directly from the expanding causal radius $R = ct$.

The expansion-driven flux of space underlies the extra-Newtonian acceleration observed in galactic dynamics.

III. GALACTIC DYNAMICS

To address the dynamics of a given galaxy, a group, or a cluster, we partition the universal flux,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_R &= \Phi_r + \Phi_{R^-} = \oint (\mathbf{a}_r + \mathbf{a}_{R^-}) \cdot d\mathbf{S}_r + \oint \mathbf{a}_{R^-} \cdot (d\mathbf{S}_R - d\mathbf{S}_r) \\ &= -4\pi GM_r - 4\pi G(M_R - M_r), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

into a local flux Φ_r and a remaining cosmic flux Φ_{R^-} . The total field $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}_r + \mathbf{a}_{R^-}$, inferred from observations, threads through the surface \mathbf{S}_r at radius r . Within this volume, the local baryonic mass M_r acts as the source of the Newtonian component $a_r(r) = GM_r(r)/r^2$. All other ordinary masses, $M_R - M_r$, total the source of the remaining universal field, $a_{R^-} = G(M_R - M_r)/R^2$, threading through the expanding shell $\mathbf{S}_R - \mathbf{S}_r$ at $R^- \approx R$. Since $r \ll R$ and $M_r \ll M_R$ for a galaxy, a group of galaxies, or even for a cluster of galaxies, $a_{R^-} \approx a_R$, manifesting as the universal threshold acceleration observed in galactic scaling laws [1–5, 7–10].

A. Isotropic spherical systems

Assuming local and global symmetry renders \mathbf{a}_r and \mathbf{a}_{R^-} radial and parallel, reducing the dynamics to a sum of magnitudes:

$$a \approx a_r + a_R = a_r \left(1 + \frac{a_R}{a_r} \right). \quad (6)$$

In dense systems, such as in the interiors of elliptical galaxies, the local Newtonian acceleration rules, $a_r/a_R > 1$ [26]. In sparser systems, such as rich clusters, where $a_r/a_R \approx 1$, the dynamics is more intricate. In even sparser systems, such as dwarf galaxies, poor clusters, and peripheral objects, the universal acceleration $a_R/a_r \gg 1$ prevails over large radii, where velocity dispersions become essentially proportional to a_R [27, 28].

The total acceleration $a \approx a_r + a_R$, multiplied by the enclosed mass M_r , defines the force balance

$$M_r \frac{\sigma^2}{r} = M_r (a_r + a_R). \quad (7)$$

For a virialized system $GM_r = \sigma^2 r$, this yields

$$\frac{\sigma^2 r}{G} \frac{\sigma^2}{r} = M_r (a_r + a_R), \quad (8)$$

which simplifies to the generalized baryonic Faber–Jackson relation [27, 29–31]

$$\sigma^4 = (a_r + a_R) GM_r. \quad (9)$$

This expression naturally recovers the observations: in the dense Newtonian limit $a_r \gg a_R$, it reduces to the standard virial theorem, while in the sparse limit $a_R \gg a_r$, it yields the characteristic dependency $\sigma^4 \propto M_r$.

The velocity dispersion balances the efflux of space into the sparser surroundings. This balance extends from the virialized core to the boundary r_b , where the local density—modeled here by a Hernquist profile—converges with the surrounding density. For the largest bound structures, this limit coincides with the turnaround radius r_{ta} , where the local density finally levels into the cosmic background ρ_M (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1. Velocity dispersions σ Eq. (9) and circular velocities v Eq. (11) compared with Newtonian expectations (thin lines) as a function of the radial distance r . Profiles for an elliptical galaxy (green), dwarf spheroidal (red), and galaxy cluster (blue)—with baryonic masses $M_o = 10^{11}, 10^7, 10^{15} M_\odot$ and scale radii $r_e = 10^4, 10^3, 10^6$ ly—are modeled using Hernquist density profiles. The spiral galaxy (black, $M_o = 10^{11} M_\odot$) is modeled with a Sérsic profile $r_e = 1.2 \times 10^4$ ly, $n = 1$. Wherever the local density exceeds the cosmic background, $\delta_\rho \equiv (1 - \rho_M/\rho_{M,r}) \gg 0$, the efflux of space into the expanding, sparser surroundings manifests itself as the universal acceleration $a_R = c/t$, sustaining velocity profiles above Newtonian predictions.

From this perspective, attributing the extra-Newtonian acceleration to a local dark matter through $\sigma^2 \propto G(M_o + M_{DM})/r$ becomes increasingly misleading as the local baryonic mass M_o decreases. In dwarf galaxies, the expansion-driven efflux dominates the dynamics, creating the illusion of a massive dark halo [32]. Conversely, the low velocity dispersions of ultra-diffuse galaxies reflect a negligible local efflux due to their sparse densities, rather than a curious absence of dark matter [33, 34]. Their high orbital velocities simply expose the efflux out of the hosting system, much like dwarf satellites that exhibit low internal dispersion despite high orbital speeds.

B. Circular acceleration

A star orbiting in a spiral galaxy experiences total acceleration

$$a = \frac{v^2}{r} \approx a_r + \frac{a_R}{2\pi} = a_o \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{a_R}{a_r} \right) = \frac{GM_r}{r^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{Mr^2}{M_r R^2} \right), \quad (10)$$

where the local Newtonian field $a_r = GM_r/r^2$ arises from the baryonic mass M_r within radius r . The universal field $a_R = GM/R^2$ arises from the flux of space drawn along with all receding masses $M - M_o \approx M$. For circular orbits, this field is averaged over the full orbital cycle by the geometric factor 2π , yielding the effective acceleration $a_R/2\pi$ [14, 35]

Analogously to spherical systems, the orbital balance $M_r v^2/r = M_r(a_r + a_R/2\pi)$ for a virialized disk $GM_r = v^2 r$ simplifies to a generalized baryonic Tully–Fisher relation

$$v^4 = GM_r(a_r + a_R/2\pi). \quad (11)$$

Orbital velocities balance the efflux of space into the sparser surroundings. Near the core, where $a_r \gg a_R/2\pi$, the intense local efflux stems from the steep gradient between the local density ρ_{M_r} and the cosmic background ρ_M . As the density—modeled here by a Sérsic profile—declines toward the periphery, the universal field $a_R/2\pi$ becomes dominant $a_R/2\pi \gg a_r$ [36]. Ultimately, the local efflux vanishes at the turnaround radius r_{ta} , where the local density levels into the cosmic background (Fig. 1).

The rotation curve remains flat across the orbits of satellite galaxies because the universal acceleration $a_R/2\pi > a_r$ dominates, not because a dark matter halo $M_{\text{DM}}(r) \propto r \Rightarrow \rho_{\text{DM}} \propto r^{-2}$ would flatten $v^2(r) = G(M_o + M_{\text{DM}}(r))/r$. Eventually, the efflux fades as the local overdensity $\delta_\rho \equiv (1 - \rho_M/\rho_{M_r})$ tends to zero and orbital velocities drop, not because the dark-matter halo would have steepened [37, 38]. This cubic fall-off toward the flux balance radius $r_{fb} = (M_o/M)^{1/3} R$ aligns with observations: Milky Way satellite galaxies lie within $r_{fb} \approx 1.4 \times 10^6$ ly, for $M_{\text{MW}} \approx 1.0 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$, while clusters of $M_{\text{CL}} \approx 1.0 \times 10^{15} M_\odot$ span $r_{fb} \approx 30 \times 10^6$ ly.

Although reminiscent of M^Odified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND), the relations in Eqs. (9) and (11) do not modify Newton’s law. Because MOND employs a cosmic-scale threshold of 10^{-10} ms^{-2} as a phenomenological fit—as if gravity itself were modified—it struggles with dwarf spheroidals, galaxy clusters, and certain gas-rich systems. From the proposed perspective, the search for a precise interpolation function $f(a_r/a_R)a_r = a$ to account for the mass discrepancy $v^2/v_b^2 = 1 + a_R/2\pi a_r$ becomes secondary [27, 28, 36].

C. Recession

Beyond the turnaround radius r_{ta} , where the local density $\rho_{M_o}(r)$ perfectly matches the cosmic background $\rho_M(r, t)$, bodies are carried apart by the universal influx of space—the Hubble flow—emanating from stellar and galactic processes throughout the universe. Outthere galaxies recede at speeds $u = \sqrt{a_R r} = c\sqrt{r/R}$, approaching c at the causal horizon.

The condition $\rho_{M_o} = \rho_M$ defines the radius of flux balance,

$$r_{fb} = \left(\frac{M_o}{M} \right)^{1/3} R = \left(\frac{M_o}{4\pi\rho_M} \right)^{1/3} = (GM_o t^2)^{1/3}. \quad (12)$$

As the expanding universe thins, this radius naturally lengthens, and structures form on ever-larger scales (Fig. 2). This scale-free growth aligns with the observed power-law autocorrelation of galaxies and voids [39, 40]. The cosmic web becomes coarser not because dark matter concentrates, but because space rarefies over time. Consequently, structures form earlier and on larger scales than predicted by Λ CDM [41, 42]. According to Eq. (12), Milky Way-sized galaxies, with $r = 150 \times 10^3$ ly and $M_o = 10^{11} M_\odot$, could have emerged as early as $t \approx 300 \times 10^6$ years (Fig. 2); younger objects, such as the Little Red Dots [43], were necessarily more compact to maintain flux balance within the denser primordial background. While protogalaxy groups began to consolidate within the first billion years, larger clusters followed as the background density continued to drop. As the present epoch is necessarily the least dense, the Local Hole is naturally near us.

As space flows along geodesics toward thermodynamic balance, the universe flattens toward a state of least curvature, and bodies shape into spheroids, settle into planes [29, 31], and galaxies align [44]. Satellite galaxies are not missing around their hosts; instead, universal acceleration, acting as a central force, has zeroed them in on stable orbits.

The homogeneous dispersion of distant galaxies and the uniformity of CMB naturally follow from matter transforming into space in the least time [14, 23], rather than from impromptu cosmic inflation. Consistent with the

FIG. 2. The age t of the universe as a function of decreasing density ρ (Eq. (13)) outlines the characteristic gravitational timescale of structure formation, from the early supranuclear densities comparable to stellar-mass black hole densities to the present-day densities of superclusters.

general principle of Newton's second law $\mathbf{F} = d\mathbf{p}/dt$, the greater the force, the faster the change. Massive stars burn brighter but fade faster than their low-mass counterparts, and early-type galaxies decline in number density with redshift faster than late-type galaxies. In essence, the higher the local density, the faster the rate of matter-to-space transformations, i.e., expansion. Thus, regardless of initial irregularities, the least-time principle drives the universe toward isotropy, culminating at heat death.

Although perturbations to the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) metric reproduce the peaks in the CMB power spectrum, they cannot account for large-scale structure formation without invoking dark matter. Since such peaks can arise from general principles, not solely from acoustic oscillations [45], the metric stretching with dark sector parameters may not faithfully model the physics of expansion. Furthermore, the FLRW metric implies a non-monotonic angular diameter distance with redshift, contradicting the intuitive, tangible expectation that an object appears smaller the farther it is [46].

When space emerges from matter, the cosmic density cannot be other than critical, as given by the differential form of Gauss's flux theorem, Poisson's equation for gravity

$$\nabla^2\phi = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{a}_R = 4\pi G\rho_M = \frac{c^2}{R^2} = \frac{1}{t^2}. \quad (13)$$

Rather than interpreting the metric fit to Type Ia supernova data as an accelerated expansion, the matter-to-space transformation via Eq. (13) dictates a decelerating rate of expansion $dH/dt = -1/t^2$ as the density of matter ρ_M decreases. This decelerating concrete expansion is consistent with the data without free parameters, since light necessarily shifts toward the red when traveling from the dense past to the rarefied present [14, 17, 46]. In this view, a photon does not just climb out of local gravitational wells—those of stars, galaxies, or clusters—but also climbs the broader, evolving potential of the aging universe. Thus, the cosmological redshift arises from the expanding spatial substance itself, not from a stretching metric, rendering the global gravitational redshift fundamentally no different from a local gravitational shift.

Accordingly, the proposed physical cosmology is consistent with interpreting observations through cosmic-scale averaging, yet it provides the physical cause for the effects often attributed to backreaction from local inhomogeneities [47, 48] or timescape models [49, 50]. It stands in clear contrast to the flawed tired-light hypothesis, as the redshift follows from the decreasing gravitational potential. Inferring from the force of expansion $F = c^4/G$, acting over the surface S_R , the negative pressure $-p = F/S_R = \rho_M c^2 \approx 10^{-9} \text{ Jm}^{-3}$, Eq. (13), arises from baryonic matter transforming into space rather than from an enigmatic dark energy.

It is worth stressing that $R = ct$ is not a model parameter but the increasing extent of spatial substance, characterized by density-dependent wave speed c . The cosmic time t totals the photon periods since the onset of expansion.

Thus, $R = ct$ should not be mistaken for a statement of linear expansion; on the contrary, the expansion is decelerating as matter is consumed for space through astrophysical transformations.

IV. DISCUSSION

Despite decades of searching, dark matter and dark energy remain unsubstantiated. What if they are merely ad hoc parameters to reconcile models with observations? What if we have misunderstood the nature of gravitation? What if gravitational attraction and cosmic expansion are simply two manifestations of one and the same physical process? After all, the characteristic acceleration 10^{-10} ms^{-2} , consistently inferred from galaxy rotation curves and velocity dispersions, is remarkably close in magnitude to the cosmic acceleration scale c/t , deduced from recession.

The apparent dichotomy between the outward acceleration of cosmic expansion and the inward acceleration of galactic dynamics dissolves when we view the vacuum not as an abstract spacetime but as a physical continuum in flux. Then, much like in hydrodynamics, an outflow of spatial substance from a local system into its expanding, sparser surroundings pulls bodies together, whereas an inflow from denser sources pushes them apart.

Since such fluxes originate from sources, this spatial substance must emerge from matter through elementary-particle reactions—notably annihilation—in stars, supernovae, and active galactic nuclei. As we have reasoned, the transformation of matter into space via Eq. (13) relates the decreasing density of matter ρ_M to a decelerating expansion rate $-dH/dt = 1/t^2 = 4\pi G\rho_M$. This physics of expansion aligns with Type Ia supernova data without free parameters and resolves the Hubble tension by definition, and renders the cosmological flatness problem null and void.

While historically confounding, the vacuum composing photons themselves rather than carrying them makes the Michelson–Morley null result trivial; the phase velocities along the two interferometer arms are invariably equal as the wave speed $c^2 = GM/R$ characterizes the spatial substance in balance with all matter.

Accordingly, variations in density give rise to frequency shifts, gravitational waves, bending, and time delay, consistent with the properties of the graviton. In turn, coherent variations in the phase of ray torsion give rise to electromagnetic phenomena, consistent with Maxwell’s equations, Poynting’s theorem, and the Lorenz gauge. The paired-photon vacuum also naturally accounts for the spectrum of space with Planck’s radiation law deriving from Bose-Einstein statistics. Conversely, any empirical evidence contradicting this physical plenum—such as the observation of a photon splitting—would falsify this unified explanation for galactic dynamics and cosmic expansion.

Unlike dark matter, the universal field of all ordinary matter is inseparable from the matter itself. Thus, abundance matching, which correlates galaxy luminosities with dark-matter halos, is neither theoretically motivated nor empirically substantiated [51, 52]. Furthermore, while dark matter struggles with the cusp-core problem, the universal gravitation of all ordinary matter is naturally flat, featureless, and far extending, lending itself to single-parameter modeling (MOND).

Despite these arguments, the flux-based explanation of galactic dynamics might be dismissed on the grounds that lensing by ordinary matter appears insufficient. The magnitude of deflection θ has been calibrated only against M_\odot from the angular difference between the light rays that graze the eclipsed Sun and those from the night sky. However, in determining θ , the parallel displacement of the two rays, nearly equal in magnitude to the deflection itself [53], has been neglected [17]. Since the deflected photon also gets delayed, the Shapiro time delay Δt , for a radio signal grazing the solar limb r_\odot , provides another calibration between lensing power and solar mass. The measured round-trip delay of $2\Delta t \approx 200 \mu\text{s}$ [54, 55] corresponds by $r_\odot\theta \approx c\Delta t$ to a deflection θ about five times greater than $\theta_{GR} = 4GM_\odot/c^2r_\odot$ [17]. It is therefore no coincidence that dark matter is estimated to be about five times more abundant than ordinary matter. Given this discrepancy between gravitational bending and time delay, lensed images of background galaxies do not substantiate dark matter; even the Bullet Cluster, often cited as decisive evidence, can be interpreted through the least-time paths of light without dark matter [14, 17].

In conclusion, the flux of space offers a natural explanation for phenomena attributed to dark matter and dark energy, respectively, a moniker for missing mass and an alias for expanding quintessence. Since effective theories with unsubstantiated parameters remain unfalsifiable, the troubles originate from having misinterpreted classical experiments of the 19th century as if the space itself—the very essence of gravitation—embodied no physical substance whatsoever.

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